

Acting and actors - the beginnings of the seventh art

In the 19th century, melodrama was the most popular stage type. A wide range of these performances, complemented by musical accompaniment and special effects, required a fierce and exaggerated style of acting (which today's audiences would dismiss as 'shmira'). Pathetics and deep feelings were appreciated and the main goal was to touch the audience. The same backdrops and costumes were used for all the plays, and as a rule the actors played the types, not developing the individual characters.

Enjoying the role

It was not until the beginning of our century that actors began to seriously engage in psychological fidelity in portraying characters, and the play as a whole began to be considered more important than individual actors. This naturalistic style marked the beginning of what we consider to be good acting today.

The pioneer of this turn towards realism was Konstantin Stanislavski (1863-1938), founder of the Moscow Art Theater (Moscow Art Theater). Stanislavski revolutionized acting by teaching his actors to think about the character of the character they are playing, believing that actors will only speak and move properly if they understand how the character thinks and feels.

The actors couldn't always relive the experiences of their characters, so he encouraged them to remember if they had ever felt something like it. He made them ask themselves, "If I were him, and in a situation like this, what would I feel and do?" . A drama played in that style would not look particularly realistic to us today, but it was something new at the time.

Developing a method

Stanislavsky's ideas, further developed by American Lee Strasberg at Actors Studio in New York, have made a strong impact on modern actors, especially filmmakers.

As films generally seek a realistic, accentuated ability to enter a role in certain separate scenes, many actors find it easier to work when fully enjoying the role. This style of acting, called the 'method', teaches actors to fully identify with characters and to act spontaneously and emotionally. Marlon Brand, Rod Steiger, Robert de Niro, Al Pacino and Mickey Rourke are among the most famous movie stars of that school.